

Assessing the Influence of Class Imbalance and Sampling Methods on Classification Performance of Some Supervised Learning Algorithms

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Abstract

Supervised learning is a paradigm in machine learning in which a model is trained based on an input and output value, which is referred to as a supervised signal. One of the most frequently used areas of supervised machine learning algorithms such as Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN), is the classification of data. Nevertheless, when the distribution of an event of interest is imbalanced, as is often the case with rare events, machine learning algorithms may yield biased results. The phenomenon of class imbalance in rare events has a detrimental impact on the reliability of the findings derived from analytical processes, resulting from the under-representation and under-estimation of minority classes. In this study, we examine the classification performance of popular supervised machine learning algorithms in the context of varying rarity scenarios and the impact of imbalanced data. This study also examines the influence of resampling techniques on the classification performance of algorithms.

Keywords: *Supervised Learning, Classification, Imbalanced Data, Resampling Techniques*

1. Introduction

In supervised machine learning, algorithms are developed that are capable of generating general patterns through the use of prior knowledge. These algorithms are then used to predict the outcome of instances that have not yet occurred. The objective of supervised machine learning algorithms is to categorize events based on the information available in classification problems (Singh et al., 2016). The capacity to accurately classify, comprehend, analyze, and predict events enables more effective decision-making processes. Studies on classification problems have demonstrated that machine learning algorithms are highly effective in classifying binary events in balanced data sets. However, the imbalance of the distribution has a negative impact on the classification performance of the algorithms. To address this issue, resampling techniques have been developed to stabilize the distribution of events in the data set, enabling their use in supervised algorithms.

Class imbalance refers to the phenomenon whereby certain classes are significantly under-represented in comparison to others within a given dataset. This issue frequently arises in contexts such as fraud detection, medical diagnosis, and the prediction of rare natural disasters or events, where the minority class instances are significantly fewer than the majority class instances (Maalouf and Trafalis, 2011). The presence of class imbalance represents a significant challenge in predictive modelling, as it can result in the generation of biased models that favor the majority class, thereby compromising the accuracy and reliability of the predictions. To address this issue, various data balancing techniques have been employed, including SMOTE, TomekLink, and hybrid techniques. The objective of these algorithms is to create a more balanced class distribution by either increasing the number of instances belonging to the minority class or decreasing the number of instances belonging to the majority class. This enhances the model's capacity to accurately predict occurrences of the minority class.

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In a study conducted in 2006, Caruana and Niculescu-Mizil performed a comprehensive analysis of LR, SVM, ANN, RF, Boosting, and other machine learning algorithms. This analysis was conducted with the objective of determining the relative performance of these algorithms in various performance metrics. Kurt et al. (2008), employed supervised learning algorithms, including logistic regression (LR), random forest (RF), and artificial neural networks (ANN), to predict coronary artery disease patients and compared their performance. In their 2020 study, Orozco-Arias et al. employed machine learning (ML) techniques, including LR, SVM and RF, to address complex tasks such as the detection and classification of transposable elements (TE) in bioinformatics. They evaluated the efficacy of 26 distinct metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1_Score, and demonstrated the stability of their results even in challenging conditions, such as imbalanced datasets and datasets with errors.

A review of the literature reveals that several studies have been conducted to investigate the impact of resampling techniques on classification performance, with the objective of achieving a more balanced data distribution. In their study, Seiffert et al. (2007) compared the performance of logistic regression, support vector machines, random forests, and other classifiers without resampling and with other resampling techniques included in SMOTE on data sets with varying levels of rarity. The results of this study demonstrate that the use of resampling is an effective method for enhancing the classification performance of datasets comprising instances of rare events. In their study, Cateni et al. (2014) developed a new sampling technique that combined oversampling and undersampling methods in imbalanced data sets. This technique was then tested on SVM and another machine learning algorithm, and its performance was compared with SMOTE and new technique. Furthermore, Ghorbani and Ghousi (2020), Jonathan et al. (2020) and Tariq et al. (2023) have made valuable contributions to the literature on the use of resampling techniques in machine learning algorithms.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the impact of resampling techniques, including oversampling, undersampling, and hybrid approaches, on the classification performance of machine learning algorithms, such as logistic regression, support vector machines, random forests, gradient boosting, and artificial neural networks, applied to imbalanced data.

The subsequent section presents algorithms for classifying data, resampling techniques, and the metrics used to evaluate classification performance. The following section presents the results of a simulation study conducted on data sets with varying degrees of imbalance. The final section comprehensively evaluates the results obtained.

2. Method

The objective of this study is to assess the classification performance of various supervised learning algorithms on imbalanced datasets. The following algorithms are analyzed: logistic regression, support vector machine, random forest, gradient boosting, and artificial neural network. In order to address the imbalance, resampling techniques such as SMOTE (oversampling), TomekLink (undersampling), and SMOTETomek (hybrid) are employed.

2.1. Logistic regression (LR)

Logistic regression is a statistical modeling technique that is widely used in various fields, such as epidemiology, econometrics, and psychology. In logistic regression, the probability, $\pi_i = P(y_i = 1)$, of a dichotomous outcome event is related to a set of explanatory variables in the form of equation (1). The intercept, represented by β_0 , and the coefficients ($\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k$) associated with the explanatory variables are used to predict the probability (Subasi and Ercelebi, 2005):

$$\text{logit}(\pi_i) = \ln\left(\frac{\pi_i}{1 - \pi_i}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ik}. \quad (1)$$

The sigmoid function, which transforms the value obtained from the logit function into a probability value between 0 and 1, and the negative log-likelihood (NLL), are given by the following equations (2) and (3), respectively:

$$P(y_i = 1|X_i) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ik}}}, \quad (2)$$

$$NLL = - \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \ln(\pi_i) + (1 - y_i) \ln(1 - \pi_i)]. \quad (3)$$

The principal objective of logistic regression is the maximization of parameter estimation, achieved through the identification of β coefficients that minimize the NLL probability within the designated training set (Kirasich et al., 2018).

2.2. Support vector machine (SVM)

The impressive ability of the Support Vector Machine (SVM) to generalize, find optimal solutions, and effectively discriminate between classes has garnered significant interest in the academic community (Cervantes et al., 2020). SVM, a supervised learning algorithm introduced by Vapnik in 1998, learns a decision boundary that distinguishes between two classes in a training dataset and uses this boundary to classify new test samples. SVM's robust performance in various applications is largely due to its strong theoretical foundation in statistical learning (Qiuwen et al., 1994). Consider a scenario where a set of n training examples (x_i, y_i) with binary outputs $y_i \in \{-1, 1\}$ is provided, representing a binary classification problem. To determine an optimal hyperplane, SVM employs a nonlinear mapping function, denoted as Φ , to project the input samples into a high-dimensional feature space (Rezvani et al., 2021). In addressing the classification problem, SVM identifies the solution with the largest margin, which satisfies the equation $y_i(w \cdot \Phi(x) + b) > 0$ for all $x_i \in X$, where w is the weight vector $w \in R^D$ and $b \in R$ is the bias term. This hyperplane, described by $w \cdot \Phi(x) + b = 0$, separates the samples in the training set. As a result, it provides a solution that maximizes the margin between the classes (Gold and Sollich, 2003).

2.3. Random forest (RF)

The random forest classifier was first proposed by Breiman in 2001. The Random Forest algorithm employs a random sampling technique, whereby a subset of the original data set is selected and used to create a new data set. This represents a subset of the original data set, with a distinct set of samples employed for each decision tree. A single tree is grown to its maximum depth on the new training data set using a combination of features. These fully developed trees remain unpruned. However, a random subset is selected from all features to identify the optimal feature at each node. This increases diversity and reduces the correlation between the trees. Each tree makes a class prediction, and the class with the majority of votes is selected as the final prediction (Pal, 2005).

Figure 1. Random forest algorithm.

2.4. Gradient boosting classifier (GBC)

Gradient boosting represents a practical approach proposed by Chen and Guestrin and is regarded as a highly regarded algorithm in the field of machine learning. A powerful learner can be created by combining weaker learners during the gradient boosting process. At each step, the new classifier is trained on the residual errors of the previous model, and features are assessed one by one until the desired accuracy is reached (Upadhyay et al., 2020). The primary disadvantage of the algorithm is that it is inherently iterative, continually constructing new trees to refine the accuracy of previous trees. This process is particularly time-consuming when applied to small data sets (Ali et al., 2023). The general process of the gradient boosting algorithm can be summarized as follows: In the initial stage of the process, an estimate is produced. Subsequently, the negative gradient is calculated using the loss function in step two. In the third step, a new learner is created with the objective of correcting the error. The fourth step involves weighting by learning rate and correcting errors. Subsequently, the predicted outcome is presented in the last step (Tyrallis et al., 2021).

2.5. Artificial neural network (ANN)

The concept of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) may be understood as a computational system that is based on the fundamental structure, processing method, and learning abilities of the human brain (Haykin, 1998). These systems are comprised of basic computational units that are designed to mimic the functions of biological neurons. These artificial neurons are also known as nodes and are distributed throughout a system in one or more layers. The connections between nodes are weighted, thus emulating biological synapses (Lorena et al., 2011).

A neural network is comprised of three principal layers: an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. In the context of modeling, it is assumed that the signal flow from the inputs (x_1, \dots, x_n) is one-directional, flowing to the output signal (O) of a neuron. This flow is given by equation (4):

$$O = f(\zeta) = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i\right), \quad (4)$$

where w_i represents the weight vector, whereas $f(\zeta)$ denotes the activation function (i.e., the mathematical functions determining the output of neurons). The variable network ζ is defined as the scalar product of the weight vector and the input vector as expressed in equation (5):

$$\zeta = w_1 x_1 + \dots + w_n x_n = w^T x. \quad (5)$$

In this context, the symbol T represents the transpose of a matrix. In a simplified scenario, the value O is derived from the following formula (6):

$$O = f(\zeta) = \begin{cases} 1, & w^T x \geq \theta \\ 0, & o.w. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Here, θ represents the threshold level (Abraham, 2005).

2.6. Resampling techniques

In classification problems, the distribution of the classes to which the data belongs may be imbalanced. This imbalance can have a significant impact on the results if the goal is to correctly classify the minor class. The typical solution is to first resample the training examples to achieve balance and then build the classification model (Xiao et al., 2021). The most widely used resampling techniques in the literature are SMOTE (oversampling), TomekLink (undersampling), and SMOTETomek (hybrid) approaches. To summarize the working principles of resampling methods in general:

- The synthetic minority oversampling technique (SMOTE), first proposed by Chawla et al. in 2002, represents an essential approach to data stabilization by way of an increase in the number of instances representing the rare category (Wang et al., 2006). While oversampling techniques have the capacity to enhance the representation of rare occurrences within a given dataset, there are instances when they may result in issues pertaining to overfitting (Hoens and Chawla, 2013).
- The TomekLink method, introduced by Tomek in 1976, refers to the process of randomly sampling a data set, whereby some observations of the majority class are excluded with the intention of obtaining a balanced data set. This approach results in the representation of rare events in the data set being enhanced (Wang et al., 2019). However, depending on the rarity level of the data set, the deletion of a significant number of data points may occur as a consequence.
- SMOTETomek, initially proposed by Batista et al. in 2003, can be defined as a hybrid approach that combines SMOTE and Tomek connectivity. SMOTE is a sub-sampling method that replicates the number of rare events until it equals the number of the major class. With TomekLink, the cleaning step is performed after data processing in the search (Wang et al., 2019). This hybrid approach ensures that the reduction of the main class does not lead to a significant loss of information, while at the same time avoiding the problem of overfitting that can result from oversampling (Hoens and Chawla, 2013).

To summarize the working principles of resampling methods in general, the balancing of classes in the SMOTE technique is achieved by reaching the density of the majority class with synthetic data generated for the rare class. In the Tomek connection, it is achieved by reducing the number of data points in the majority class, thereby bringing it

closer to the rare class. In the hybrid approach, data augmentation is achieved using SMOTE, while data reduction is accomplished through TomekLink (Werner et al., 2023).

2.7. Performance metrics

When machine learning algorithms are applied to a dataset associated with binary classification, it is essential to have information about their correct classification performance to make effective inferences. In order to determine the degree to which the minor class is correctly predicted, it is possible to make use of various performance metrics, including accuracy (ACC), precision (Prec), recall (Rec), and F1_Score. The confusion matrix used to calculate these metrics can be defined as follows.

Table 1. Hyperparameters used in the search.

Observed	Predicted	
	1	0
1 (minor class)	True Positive	False Negative
0 (major class)	False Positive	True Negative

The calculation formulas for the performance metrics included in this study, as derived from the confusion matrix, are as follows:

Accuracy (ACC) represents the overall correctness of the model, defined as the proportion of true positive and true negative predictions among all predictions:

$$ACC = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}. \tag{7}$$

Precision (Prec) is a measure of the proportion of correctly identified positive instances, and is therefore crucial in scenarios where false positives are costly:

$$Prec = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}. \tag{8}$$

Recall (Rec), also known as sensitivity or true positive rate, is defined as the proportion of true positive predictions among all actual positive instances:

$$Rec = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}. \tag{9}$$

F1_Score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing an integrated metric for balancing both concerns:

$$F1_{score} = 2 \left(\frac{Prec \times Rec}{Prec + Rec} \right). \tag{10}$$

Where TP (True Positive) indicates that class 1 is classified as 1, TN (True Negative) indicates that class 0 is classified as class 0, FP (False Positive) indicates that class 0 is classified as class 1, and FN (False Negative) indicates that class 1 is classified as class 0.

3. Simulation Study Results and Discussion

The efficacy of the algorithms utilized for modeling binary events was evaluated through a simulation study involving the generation of five instances with varying rarity levels. In this study, high-dimensional models with $p = 10$ variable complexities were investigated. In the model, the standardized coefficients β_i are set to 1, and the explanatory variables are assumed to follow a normal distribution, $X_i \sim N(0,1)$ ($i = 1,2, \dots, 10$). As β_0 in the model determines the proportion of the event of interest in the data set, it is of great importance to represent this value in the most accurate manner. In the case of an imbalanced distribution, the minor class exhibits low frequencies, and its effects may not be noticeable in small sample sizes. Consequently, the sample size was set to 1000 in order to increase statistical power and to enable more robust analysis of the effects of imbalance. Noting that the minor event of interest is represented as “1” and the class distributions as 0%:1%, different scenarios with class distributions of 99:1, 95:5, 90:10, 85:15, and 80:20 each with a sample size of $n=1000$ are examined.

Then, the binary event with the above settings is generated as

$$y(\pi(x)) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \pi < u \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where u is a dummy variable from.

In the simulation, which was written in *Python Spyder 5.4.3* and performed with 100 replications, the data sets were randomly divided into training and test sets in a 67%:33% ratio. First, the model was constructed, and prediction values were obtained for the data with an imbalanced distribution. Subsequently, the data were balanced with resampling techniques using the *imblearn* library (Lemaître et al., 2017). Finally, the necessary metrics were calculated to compare the performances.

Table 2 presents the values of the optimized parameters for the algorithms. The program is designed to accommodate all possible hyperparameter combinations. The results indicate the values of the combination that exhibited the highest success rate.

Table 2. Hyperparameters used in the search.

Method	Parameter
SVM	Kernel: Linear, Sigmoid, Rbf Regularization parameter: 0.1, 0.5, 1,10
RF	n-estimator: 10, 50, 100 Criterion: Gini, Entropy
GBC	Learning rate: 0.01, 0.1, 0.2
ANN	Activation: ReLU, Sigmoid, Tanh Optimizer: Adam, SGD

Table 3. Accuracy (ACC) results of algorithms.

ACC	Methods	Rarity Levels				
		1%	5%	10%	15%	20%
Without Sampling (WOS)	LR	0.995	0.937	0.917	0.901	0.867
	SVM	0.995	0.934	0.909	0.902	0.855
	RF	0.995	0.933	0.912	0.867	0.840
	GBC	0.994	0.924	0.907	0.855	0.841
	ANN	0.995	0.933	0.904	0.887	0.845
SMOTE	LR	0.902	0.842	0.848	0.806	0.802
	SVM	0.892	0.816	0.852	0.798	0.729
	RF	0.966	0.905	0.887	0.840	0.810
	GBC	0.915	0.851	0.856	0.810	0.795
	ANN	0.952	0.872	0.817	0.778	0.759
TomekLink	LR	0.989	0.937	0.905	0.894	0.852
	SVM	0.989	0.936	0.901	0.890	0.853
	RF	0.989	0.935	0.882	0.873	0.825
	GBC	0.986	0.929	0.883	0.870	0.819
	ANN	0.988	0.932	0.883	0.873	0.825
SMOTETomek	LR	0.899	0.815	0.839	0.806	0.819
	SVM	0.887	0.788	0.843	0.792	0.817
	RF	0.953	0.893	0.882	0.836	0.826
	GBC	0.883	0.868	0.808	0.765	0.812
	ANN	0.947	0.820	0.813	0.779	0.778

Upon analysis of the ACC values presented in Table 3, it can be observed that LR exhibits the highest performance values at the 1% rarity level, regardless of the resampling procedure employed. This is, in fact, an expected result. As the distribution becomes more balanced, the performance of correctly classifying the minor class decreases, depending on the rarity level. This is because the dominant class is correctly classified. This result indicates that the ACC metric is not an optimal metric for performance evaluation in general. Regarding the model's level of rarity, it can be concluded that similar observations can be made for algorithms other than LR. In terms of the ACC metric, the RF algorithm demonstrates superior performance in oversampling and hybrid techniques compared to other algorithms. Conversely, the LR algorithm exhibits superior performance in undersampling techniques.

Table 4. Precision (Prec) results of algorithms.

Prec	Methods	Rarity Levels				
		1%	5%	10%	15%	20%
WOS	LR	1.000	0.676	0.623	0.754	0.723
	SVM	1.000	0.997	0.796	0.764	0.687
	RF	1.000	0.514	0.621	0.647	0.668
	GBC	0.770	0.314	0.513	0.794	0.630
	ANN	0.970	0.967	0.692	0.706	0.708
SMOTE	LR	0.080	0.264	0.393	0.417	0.506
	SVM	0.074	0.236	0.393	0.408	0.406
	RF	0.080	0.333	0.459	0.458	0.525
	GBC	0.054	0.253	0.390	0.402	0.494
	ANN	0.090	0.297	0.359	0.384	0.455
TomekLink	LR	0.940	0.567	0.677	0.680	0.649
	SVM	1.000	0.995	0.743	0.756	0.674
	RF	1.000	0.485	0.523	0.566	0.569
	GBC	0.361	0.387	0.743	0.727	0.673
	ANN	0.894	0.866	0.677	0.628	0.639
SMOTETomek	LR	0.101	0.237	0.335	0.418	0.556
	SVM	0.093	0.217	0.312	0.400	0.551
	RF	0.062	0.293	0.378	0.458	0.588
	GBC	0.046	0.254	0.276	0.352	0.551
	ANN	0.078	0.243	0.320	0.393	0.520

Upon examination of Table 4 in terms of the Prec metric, it becomes evident that SVM demonstrates superior performance at the most rarity levels when no sampling is conducted. However, when the distribution is balanced with oversampling or hybrid approaches, RF performs well, and when balanced with undersampling, SVM demonstrates good correct classification performance.

Table 5. Recall (Rec) results of algorithms.

Rec	Methods	Rarity Levels				
		1%	5%	10%	15%	20%
WOS	LR	0.000	0.127	0.310	0.539	0.518
	SVM	0.000	0.003	0.095	0.534	0.479
	RF	0.000	0.062	0.196	0.322	0.367
	GBC	0.000	0.111	0.267	0.090	0.454
	ANN	0.160	0.005	0.259	0.519	0.448
SMOTE	LR	0.659	0.851	0.847	0.818	0.798
	SVM	0.667	0.855	0.779	0.835	0.743
	RF	0.177	0.511	0.545	0.509	0.596
	GBC	0.364	0.668	0.653	0.612	0.655
	ANN	0.301	0.661	0.724	0.748	0.776
TomekLink	LR	0.016	0.179	0.404	0.407	0.503
	SVM	0.002	0.001	0.288	0.309	0.467
	RF	0.011	0.117	0.209	0.260	0.377
	GBC	0.190	0.110	0.077	0.067	0.111
	ANN	0.024	0.041	0.303	0.392	0.441
SMOTETomek	LR	0.742	0.823	0.804	0.802	0.805
	SVM	0.742	0.850	0.617	0.806	0.804
	RF	0.153	0.447	0.472	0.600	0.649
	GBC	0.350	0.527	0.675	0.698	0.698
	ANN	0.300	0.666	0.717	0.734	0.774

A review of the Rec metric indicates that the performance of LR improves as the distribution becomes more balanced without the need for resampling. When resampling techniques are considered, it can be observed that LR exhibits good classification performance at most rarity levels. In most cases in which LR is ineffective, SVM performs well.

Table 6. F1_Score results of algorithms.

F1_Score	Methods	Rarity Levels				
		1%	5%	10%	15%	20%
WOS	LR	0.000	0.205	0.407	0.625	0.600
	SVM	0.000	0.005	0.141	0.624	0.561
	RF	0.000	0.105	0.291	0.426	0.469
	GBC	0.000	0.156	0.345	0.158	0.525
	ANN	0.160	0.005	0.268	0.570	0.493
SMOTE	LR	0.139	0.401	0.534	0.551	0.618
	SVM	0.130	0.368	0.518	0.546	0.524
	RF	0.100	0.396	0.493	0.479	0.556
	GBC	0.091	0.360	0.484	0.482	0.561
	ANN	0.121	0.400	0.461	0.501	0.567
TomekLink	LR	0.022	0.261	0.500	0.505	0.563
	SVM	0.003	0.002	0.402	0.413	0.544
	RF	0.016	0.181	0.293	0.349	0.450
	GBC	0.193	0.150	0.126	0.121	0.186
	ANN	0.024	0.044	0.330	0.415	0.449
SMOTETomek	LR	0.172	0.366	0.470	0.548	0.656
	SVM	0.160	0.343	0.408	0.533	0.653
	RF	0.082	0.349	0.415	0.517	0.615
	GBC	0.079	0.340	0.387	0.466	0.614
	ANN	0.109	0.327	0.423	0.489	0.606

Upon examination of Table 6, which shows the F1_Scores, it becomes evident that LR exhibits an improvement in its correct classification performance as the distribution becomes more balanced. This phenomenon is observed to be consistent across all resampling techniques, including WOS. At the 1% rarity level, where the distribution is the most imbalanced, both the ANN in the WOS and the GBC in the undersampling technique have provided better results than the other algorithms.

4. Conclusions

The simulation study examines the performance of different algorithms at varying levels of imbalance. The evaluation of the algorithms is based on performance metrics such as accuracy (ACC), precision (Prec), recall (Rec), and F1_Score. The results indicate that the LR algorithm generally exhibits the highest performance. However, when imbalanced data is balanced using resampling techniques, other algorithms may perform better.

When resampling techniques are not employed at a 1% level, where the distribution imbalance is the greatest, the accuracy performance of all algorithms is the highest, and they are very similar to each other, even identical in most cases. This indicates that the ACC performance measure is not a reliable indicator of the algorithms' effectiveness. The reason for this is that the algorithms correctly predict the major class, resulting in high accuracy values. As the distribution becomes more balanced, the performance of correctly classifying the minor class decreases. This finding is consistent with the results observed when resampling techniques are used.

In general, when resampling techniques are evaluated for all imbalanced distributions, RF performs best when SMOTE and SMOTETomek resampling techniques are used, while LR performs best when TomekLink resampling technique is used.

When the tables are evaluated in terms of Prec, it can be observed that, when no resampling (WOS) techniques are used, all algorithms except GBC demonstrate high performance at 1% imbalanced distribution. SMOTE and SMOTETomek resampling techniques exhibit an increase in classification performance as the distribution becomes balanced, while TomekLink resampling method demonstrates performance similar to WOS. RF and SVM are the algorithms that perform better in terms of Prec measure.

When the Rec tables are analyzed, it is observed that the correct classification performance generally increases when the distribution becomes balanced, regardless of whether the WOS or resampling techniques are used. In terms of this performance metric, it can be concluded that the SVM and LR algorithms are generally more successful than other algorithms. The SMOTETomek resampling method seems to be the technique that provides the highest correct classification performance of all algorithms.

Finally, an evaluation of the tables for the F1_Score performance metric regardless of whether the resampling technique is used or not indicates that a more balanced distribution significantly improves the classification performance of this performance metric. The LR algorithm has the best performance for this metric for all techniques and distribution imbalances.

The results of the study demonstrate that resampling techniques are crucial for enhancing classification performance on datasets with an imbalance in their distribution of classes, as previously observed by Seiffert et al. 2007. In particular, the RF and SVM algorithms demonstrate superior performance when different balancing techniques are applied. The findings indicate the efficacy of resampling techniques in addressing imbalanced datasets in machine learning applications. Future work could focus on optimizing the parameters of resampling techniques in unsupervised learning algorithms and to more thoroughly evaluate the effects of different degrees of imbalance on algorithm performance. Such efforts will contribute to improving methodologies for effectively addressing class imbalance issues in machine learning applications.

Author Contribution Statements

O. Alpay was solely responsible for the study design, implementation, analysis, and manuscript preparation.

Ethics committee approval

This article does not require ethics committee approval.

Conflict of interest statement

This article has no conflicts of interest with any individual or institution.

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